

IMPORTANT ISSUES OF ORGANIZING ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11109260>

Annotation. The thesis describes economic activity in the world today: production of economic energy, production process and production, cost of its introduction and production.

Key words: economy, economy, information, information, large volume,

Introduction.

Another new term is entering our life in the current rapidly growing globalization process. This concept is considered to be a force that will fundamentally change our lives, but also ushers in a new era in our country, and the name of this force is "Digital Economy". What is the digital economy? Who and what country introduced this term to science, it is appropriate to make a brief comment about it.

Digital economy is an economic activity in which the main factor in production and service is information in the form of numbers, with the help of processing a large amount of information and analyzing the result of this processing of various types is to implement more effective solutions than the previous system in production, service, technologies, devices, storage, product delivery. In other words, the digital economy is an activity connected with the development of online services, electronic payments, internet trade and other types of industries, digital computer technologies.

Basically, we can include e-commerce, internet banking, electronic payments, internet advertising and at the same time internet games as the main elements of the development of the digital economy.

The term digital economy was coined in 1995 by the University of Massachusetts introduced by scientist Nicolas Negraponte. It's almost out of the system now used by all developed countries of the world, "Digital" countries today Norway, Sweden and Switzerland are considered. The 10 countries with the most developed digital economy include the United States, Great Britain, Denmark, Finland, Singapore, South Korea and Hong Kong¹.

¹ <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcio/definition/digital-economy>

Digital economy in our country, like the countries of the world is developing. After the introduction of information technologies into our daily life, new opportunities are emerging in the life of our people. Nowadays any type that we need without leaving our home ordering and receiving consumer goods and much more we can save our time. But it is worth noting that our country is a country of digital economy compared to its potential, it is developing more slowly and several there are some problems in the fields. In these areas and in the system there are several problems, we can see them below. It is not a secret to anyone that problems related to the Internet (low speed and quality of the Internet), lack of information technology specialists or their departure to foreign countries, these are common problems and are being corrected day by day. We can also include banking, finance and accounting in these fields.

"Actions on the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the strategy" of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. 4947 ²"Strengthening macroeconomic stability aimed at further development and liberalization of the economy and maintaining high economic growth rates of the national economy by maintaining its stability and improving the investment environment It is not for nothing that "active attraction of foreign investments in sectors and regions of our country's economy" is defined as one of the main tasks. How urgent is the development of our economy In view of this, a number of important decisions were taken by our government in order to rapidly develop digital economy and information and communication technologies in our country and further development of the state and society in our republic. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan named 2020 as the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy"³, the President's Decree No. PF-5349 dated February 19, 2018 "To further develop the field of information technologies and communications" "Decree on development measures" and "Uzbekistan Decision PQ-3832 of 03.07.2018 "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", as well as the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of August 31, 2018, which defines the goals and objectives of the digital economy "On the introduction of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan and further Adoption of decisions on additional measures for development is legal for the development of the digital economy in our country in order to apply the digital economy to the state management system, create conditions for the rapid

² PD4947

³ "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy"

development of modern information technologies, and ensure information security. we can say that he created the foundations no exaggeration.

Summary.

Now the main and relevant works are developed in quick pictures, A fully digitized system is planned in our country. The world is now fully digitized, that is, sales, markets, buyer and customer relations are all working online. We know that now the whole world is artificial are raising their economic positions with the help of cloud technologies on the basis of intellect, and in turn, our use of these systems will first of all ensure the well-being of our people, and we will take a step to a new stage in the development of the economy of our country. Development strategy in all areas and of course digital emphasizing that there are defects in the economy and measures to eliminate these defects, it requires further development of the digital economy, which has entered our lives rapidly, and urgent solutions to the problems.

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